

IMPEACHMENT OF ARBITRAL AWARD IN NIGERIA: THE FUNCTIONALITY OF AWARD REVIEW TRIBUNAL IN THE ARBITRATION AND MEDIATION ACT 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19916047>

Abstract

The Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 made provisions for the impeachment and setting aside of arbitral award under the Act in section 55. The section made it that a party to the arbitration agreement who is dissatisfied with the arbitral award as rendered by the arbitral tribunal has a right to file his application for the impeachment of the award in the court. Section 55(3) of the Act established the grounds for the impeachment of arbitral awards in Nigeria. Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 made a new provision for Award Review Tribunal (ART). Award Review Tribunal is a voluntary and optional appellate mechanism newly introduced in the Act. The question that arises is, what is the hardship in section 55 of the Act which section 56 is to cure or address? Is Award Review Tribunal (ART) an appellate tribunal sitting on appeal on the arbitral award rendered by the First Instance Arbitral Tribunal? Is the decision of the Award Review Tribunal on any matter decided by its final or is it still subject to the jurisdiction of the High Court pursuant to section 55 of the Act? What is the law on this matter with respect to the practice in other developed countries? Is Award Review Tribunal not a waste of time with intent to introduce delay, second level of arbitral cost, and hardship? Is it devoid of additional cost and hardship? It is to address these issues and questions that we have embarked on this mission. It must be mentioned that the essence of this research work and its emphasis are not on impeachment of arbitral award in Nigeria but on the Award Review Tribunal (ART) which is a new innovation in the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023. In order to do justice to this topic, efforts must be made to summarize meaning and grounds for impeachment of arbitral award as both issues are related. Award Review Tribunal is an offshoot of impeachment process in arbitration practice.

Keywords: *Functionality, Arbitral Award, Award Review Tribunal, Impeachment, Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023.*

1. Introduction: The former arbitration Act of Nigeria, that is, the Arbitration and Conciliation Act CAP A18 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004 provided for the impeachment of domestic and international arbitral award in sections 29, 30 and 48 of the Act. There was no provision made in the Act for Award Review Tribunal by a second arbitral tribunal. Impeachment as provided in the said Act

(Arbitration and Conciliation Act) was for legal incapacity, invalidity of arbitration agreement, misconduct, error of law, jurisdictional issues, arbitrability, and public policy reasons.

Arbitration and Mediation Act in its section 55 of the Act provided for the impeachment of both domestic and foreign arbitral awards in Nigeria. The Act further provided for remission of arbitral award to the arbitral tribunal.¹ The provision for the remission of arbitral award in section 55(6) of the Act is commendable. The grounds for impeachment of arbitral award which we shall review in summary were also set out in the Act.² The Act however, did not stop at impeachment as in section 55 of the Act but went further and provided for Award Review Tribunal (ART).³ The Award Review Tribunal is to be the second arbitral tribunal on the same subject matter but particularly on the arbitral award as rendered by the First Instance Arbitral Tribunal. The grounds for the review and the guiding principles are as set out in section 55(3) of the Act. The Award Review Tribunal is not a court and the review is not a judicial review in the strict legal and judicial sense. Where after the review by the Award Review Tribunal, the aggrieved party is still dissatisfied, he can file his application to High Court pursuant to section 55 of the Act either on the whole or part of the award.

It is for the parties while entering into the arbitration agreement to specify if arbitral awards could be referred to Award Review Tribunal or not. Award Review Tribunal cannot be imposed on the parties where they failed to provide for it in their arbitration agreement. The simple implication of this statement is that it is for the parties to provide in their arbitration agreement for the review of an arbitral award on any of the grounds set out in section 55(3) of the Act.⁴ Where the arbitration agreement of the parties provided for Award Review Tribunal, the arbitral tribunal who heard the matter and rendered arbitral award shall be referred to as the First Instance Tribunal.⁵

2. Impeachment of Arbitral Awards

The term impeachment means attack on the arbitral award with intent to set it aside, vary, qualify, severe, or render it invalid. It is a legal process where a party challenges, sets aside, or vacates an arbitral award, usually within a specified period of time, when it is believed to be unjust, biased, or outside the arbitral tribunal's authority. It acts as a necessary safeguard for fairness, allowing the courts to sever, or invalidate flawed arbitral awards that violate due process, public policy, misconduct provisions, or the arbitral agreement, rather than accepting them as final. The process of impeachment does not always set aside the whole arbitral award as the courts may only remove the defective portions if they can be severed from the baptized portion or valid parts. Parties to arbitration agreement expect that the arbitral award when made shall be fair, final, and just but this is not always the case. When the arbitral award as made by the arbitral tribunal fails to meet the fair and just expectation of the parties, the law confers on them the remedy of impeachment of the arbitral award.⁶ In impeachment process, the courts do not approach the award with a meticulous legal eye endeavoring to pick holes, inconsistencies and faults with objective of upsetting or frustrating the process of arbitration practice. The approach always is to read an arbitral award in a

¹ Section 55(6) of the Act.

² Section 55(3) of the Act.

³ Section 56 of the Act.

⁴ Section 56 of the Act.

⁵ Section 56(4)(a) of the Act

⁶ *Adwork Ltd. v. Nigeria Airways Ltd.* (2002)2NWLR (Pt.645)415.

reasonable and commercial way, expecting as usual that there will be no substantial fault that can be found. The court is not expected to treat or interpret the award with the same standard as a judgment of the court.⁷

The courts should not and are not expected to unnecessarily interfere with the arbitral awards unless there are compelling reasons and need for them to do so. This implies that the court should not juxtapose its own standard of justice on the arbitration proceedings and arbitral award but rather to look at the arbitral award and determine whether on the state of the law as understood by the arbitrators and as stated on the face of the award, the arbitrators complied with the law as they themselves rightly or wrongly perceived it. The approach here is subjective as the judge simply takes the position of the arbitrator and not above him and determines the issue in that perspective.⁸

Section 55 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act, 2023 made copious provisions for the impeachment of arbitral awards in Nigeria. Section 55(3) of the Act specifically set out in great detail grounds pursuant to which an arbitral award could be impeached in Nigeria. A party to the arbitration agreement who is desirous of impeaching arbitral award shall file his application to the court. The court to which the application shall be filed is the court which but for the arbitration agreement has original jurisdiction to hear and determine the matter.⁹The application for impeachment shall be made within three months after the making of the arbitral award.¹⁰ The courts have at various times made conflicting decisions on the time limitation for impeachment of arbitral award.¹¹ The three months time limitation as specified in section 55(4) is not subject to extension by the court because the word used is that “an application for setting aside shall be made after three months have elapsed.” The court has no right to extend the time fixed for impeachment as the Act failed to confer such power on it and also as the right of extension of time for doing anything pursuant to the Act can only be done by the arbitral tribunal and not the court.¹²

We shall now summarize the grounds for impeachment of awards. Only a party to the arbitration agreement can apply for impeachment of the award on any of the grounds set out in section 55(3) of the Act.¹³

(a) **Legal Incapacity:** The parties to the arbitration agreement must have the legal capacity to contract. This is because the capacity to enter into arbitration agreement is same with the capacity to contract. Section 55 (3) (a) (i) provides that the court may set aside an arbitral award where a party to the arbitration agreement was under some legal incapacity. The New York Convention in it Article v(1)(a) made a similar provision. The applicable rules governing incapacity are not uniform. For a natural person, that is, a human person, capacity is dependent on the law of the place of residence, whereas for corporation or company, capacity is dependent on the law of incorporation or the place of business. A person who has

⁷ *Zermalt Holding S.A. v. Nu-Life Upholstery Repair Ltd.* (1985)275 Estate Gazette 1134.

⁸ *Baker Marine v. Chevron Nig. Ltd.* (2000)12NWLR (Pt.681)393. *MTN Nig. Comm. Ltd v. Etuk Habsan* (2017) NWLR (Pt.1598)394. Greg C.Nwakoby, *The Law and Practice of Commercial Arbitration in Nigeria*, 3rd Ed. Chenglo Ltd. Enugu, 2925, p.204.

⁹ *Afcon Nig. Ltd. V. Registered Trustees of Ikoyi Club 1938*(1996) FHCLR371. *C/F N.N.P.C. v. Fung Tai Engr. Co. Ltd.* (2023)15NWLR (Pt.1906)117.

¹⁰ Section 55(4) of the Act

¹¹ *K.S.U.D.B. v. Fanz Construction Co. Ltd* (1990)4NWLR (Pt.142)1 where the court decided that impeachment shall be within six weeks. *Ekeng Ita v. Edet Idiok* 4 N.L.R. 100 where the court decided that impeachment shall be within 15days.

¹² Sections 64 & 66 of the Act. As at the time of the application for impeachment of the arbitral award, the arbitral tribunal is *functus officio* as its right to interfere in the matter has been extinguished hence it cannot extend the time for impeachment. The court cannot also extend the time limitation for impeachment because the Act has made it that after the three months period, the right of the aggrieved party becomes statute barred.

¹³ *U.B.A. v. Trident Consultant Ltd.* (2023)33WRN1

the right and capacity to enter into a contract has also the right to submit the contract to arbitration agreement. An infant has the right and capacity to enter into arbitration agreement if the contract is for his benefit or supply of necessities. An agreement entered into by an infant is voidable unless it is for his benefit.¹⁴

(b) **Invalidity of the arbitration agreement:** The agreement to arbitrate must be valid for the arbitral award to be valid. Where the arbitration agreement is invalid for any reason whatsoever, the resultant arbitral award shall be invalid. Arbitral award rendered by the arbitral tribunal will be impeached on the successful application of a party if the arbitration agreement is legally invalid. ¹⁵An arbitration agreement may be said to be invalid where the arbitration agreement is undermined by fraud, undue influence, unconscionability, duress, mistake or misrepresentation, improper procurement, and pervasiveness.¹⁶

(c) **Lack of Fair Hearing:** The law requires that the parties must be given fair hearing and be heard in full before decision or arbitral award is made in their matter. Fair hearing is a constitutional requirement as enshrined in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended). Section 36(1) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as amended provides that “in determination of his civil right and obligation, including any question or determination by or against any government or authority, a person shall be entitled to fair hearing within a reasonable time by a court or other tribunal established by law and constituted in such a manner as to secure its independence.” Other tribunal as used in this section includes arbitral tribunal constituted in accordance with the provisions of the Arbitration and Mediation Act. Section 30 of the Arbitration and Mediation Act also made provisions for equal treatment and fair hearing. The section provides that “in any arbitral proceedings, the arbitral tribunal shall ensure that the parties are- (a) treated equally and that each party is given reasonable opportunity of presenting its case; and (b) accorded a fair resolution of the dispute without unnecessary delay or expense.”

The arbitral tribunal is expected to observe certain minimal procedural standard if its award is to be enforced by the court. This implies that the parties must be given adequate opportunity to present their case, be heard in full with their witnesses. It also means that adequate notices must be given to the parties for every arbitral proceedings and hearing. The party to the arbitration agreement initiating the arbitral proceedings must serve adequate notice or written communication to the adverse party.¹⁷

d. Lack of Jurisdiction: Jurisdiction is the authority which the arbitral tribunal has to deal with the matter referred to it.¹⁸ It is the authority which an arbitrator has to decide matters that are presented before it or to take cognizance of matters presented in a formal way for its decision.¹⁹ It is a legal power and authority of an arbitral tribunal to make valid decision binding on the parties concerned in any matter

¹⁴ *Slade & Anor v. Methrodent Ltd.* (1953)2Q.B .112

¹⁵ Section 55(3) a(ii) of the Act which provides that arbitral award will be impeached where a party who makes the application furnishes proof that the arbitration agreement is not valid under the law to which the parties have subjected it.

¹⁶ Greg C. Nwakoby, *the Law and Practice of Commercial Arbitration in Nigeria*, 2nd Ed. Snaap Press Ltd. .p.46. See also Greg C. Nwakoby, *The Law and Practice of Commercial Arbitration in Nigeria*, Chenglo Ltd., Enugu, 2025, pp 214 -215.

¹⁷ Article 3(1) of the First Schedule Arbitration Rules of the Arbitration and Mediation Act.

¹⁸ John B. Saunders, *Words and Phrases Defined*, 2nd Ed. Butterworth, London, 1969, 113

¹⁹ *Black's Law Dictionary*, 853. *Anisimic Ltd v. Foreign Compensation* (1986)2 All ER 986.

brought properly before it.²⁰It is the arbitration agreement entered into by the parties that confer jurisdiction on the arbitral tribunal to arbitrate for the parties hence “no arbitration agreement no arbitration”.

Lack of jurisdiction does not mean one thing but many things. The issue of jurisdiction may arise at various or different stages of arbitration. It could arise as a result of none arbitration agreement between the parties, that is lack of jurisdiction.²¹ It could also arise in a situation wherein the parties entered into arbitration agreement but the arbitral tribunal went beyond what was agreed or referred by the parties, that is, excess of jurisdiction. Lack of jurisdiction could also arise in a situation where the subject matter is not arbitrable because of its public nature or because of certain legislative enactments (criminal matters, divorce matters, taxation matters, etc). Sections 55(3) (a) (IV) (v) of the Act provide that the court may set aside an arbitral award, where-

(iv) The award deals with a dispute not contemplated by or does not fall within the terms of the submission to arbitration,

(v) the award contains decisions on matters which are beyond the scope of the submission to arbitration, provided that, if the decisions on matters submitted to arbitration can be separated from those not submitted, only that part of the award which contains decisions on matters not submitted to arbitration may be set aside.

Sequel to above stated fact, where the arbitral tribunal deals with issues not contemplated in the agreement or issues falling beyond the agreement of the parties or their submission, the award will be set aside for lack of or excess of jurisdiction provided always that where what is beyond the scope of submission of the parties can be severed, the court will sever the excess part and retain the once falling within the agreement.

e. Wrong Composition of Arbitral Tribunal or Arbitral Procedure: The parties to the arbitration agreement have right to appoint their arbitrators or specify the number of the arbitrator or procedure for the appointment. Where the parties failed to specify the number of arbitrators for the arbitration, the arbitration shall be constituted of a sole arbitrator.²²The current section 6(2) of the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 is in sharp contrast with the provisions of the repealed Arbitration and Conciliation Act (L.F.N.) 2004 which in its section 6 provides that where the parties to the arbitration agreement failed to specify the number of arbitrators in their agreement, the number shall be deemed to be three. The provision of the former Act is preferred to the current provision as it gave the parties the right to appoint one arbitrator each in the absence of specification of number of arbitrators. It is also preferred because it gave room for appointment of more arbitrators in complex disputes and matters where one arbitrator may not be able to undertake the proceedings alone.

Where the parties specified the qualifications for the arbitrators or the number of arbitrators to be appointed to conduct the arbitral proceedings, any appointment made without regard and adherence to

²⁰ *Chidi Ekwueme v. Sani Zakari* (1972) ECLSR 1.

²¹ *ibid*

²² Greg C. Nwakoby, *the Law and Practice of Commercial Arbitration in Nigeria 2nd Ed.* Snaap Press Ltd. 46. Greg Chukwudi Nwakoby, Nwakoby Blessing Chidinma, Nwakoby Kenechukwu Gregory, “Impeachment of Arbitral Award: Review of Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023,” *Academic Journal of Legal Studies and Research*, Vol.10, No.6 Nov-December, 2024, pp1-23. Section 6(1) of the Act.

the specifications of the parties in their arbitration agreement will be invalid and impeached as being contrary to the terms of the arbitration agreement. It is important to state that once the composition of the arbitral tribunal is wrong, the arbitral award resulting there from shall be impeached and it is absolutely immaterial if the wrong composition affected only one or two arbitrators in an arbitration conducted by three or more arbitrators. The question that may often arise is whether a unanimous award could be set aside if the appointment of one of the three arbitrators was successfully challenged. The Act has made it that the improper composition of the arbitrator(s) will presumably affect the arbitral award. This position of the Act did not create any exception. It is immaterial that if the two properly appointed arbitrators were reconstituted with a new neutral arbitrator, the two arbitrators will still retain their majority award. The standard in evaluating the extent to which the bias of one arbitrator could affect an award is very light as the standard is not high. The fact that the award is a unanimous decision of the majority is absolutely immaterial and irrelevant. What is important is that an arbitrator has bias or is partial and not independent in the matter.²³

f. Arbitrability and Public Policy: Not all matters are arbitrable in Nigeria. Arbitrability is somewhat related to jurisdiction. Section 55(3)(b)(i)(ii) of the Act provides that an award shall be impeached if the Court finds that the “subject matter of the dispute is otherwise not capable of settlement by arbitration under the laws of Nigeria, or award is against public policy of Nigeria.”²⁴ It is not all subject matters that can be referred to arbitration. Only disputes affecting the civil rights and obligations of people which can be compromised by accord and satisfaction may be referred to arbitration.²⁵ The fair determination of arbitrability is as decided by the court in *United World Ltd Inc. v. M.T.S. Ltd.*²⁶ that the dispute or matter which the parties to an arbitration agreement agreed to refer must consist of a justiciable issue triable civilly. The main consideration is whether the matter or difference can be compromised lawfully by way of accord and satisfaction. Criminal matters, tax and public revenue cases, and dissolution of marriage under the Act (divorce) are not subject to arbitration and cannot be referred to ADR generally as the law has made it that they are subject to courts of competent jurisdiction. According to Prof. Parker, “the central theme in non-arbitrability cases is a concern that society will be injured by arbitration of public claims. Courts expressed a fear that public law issues are too complicated for arbitrators to handle or that arbitrators are like foxes guarding the chicken coop, with a pro-business bias that will lead to under enforcement of the laws designed to protect the public.”²⁷

The principle of arbitrability hangs majorly on two fundamental premise and principles. The first being that some disputes by their very nature fail under the exclusive jurisdiction of the courts and are therefore not subject to arbitration agreement and proceedings at all. An example of this is the dissolution of marriage contracted under the Act which pursuant to the provisions of the Matrimonial Causes Act is subject to the jurisdiction of the State High Court. Secondly, some disputes are required under some

²³ Nwakoby Greg Chukwudi, Nwakoby Blessing Chidinma, and Nwakoby Gregory Kenekwuwu, “Impeachment of Arbitral Award: A Review of Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023”, *Academic Journal of Legal Studies and Research*, Vol.10, Issue 06, November – December 2024, pp. 1-22.

²⁴ Article v (2) of the New York Convention.

²⁵ *Baker v. Townshend* (1817)7Taunt 422. Nwakoby Greg Chukwudi, Nwakoby Blessing Chidinma and Nwakoby Gregory Kenekwuwu, “Impeachment of Arbitral Award: A Review of Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023” *Academic Journal of Legal Studies and Research*, Vol. 10, Issue 06, Nov. – December, 2024, pp.1-22

²⁶ ((1998)10NWLR (Pt.568)106 at 110.

²⁷ Parker, “National Law and Commercial Justice: Safeguarding Procedural Integrity in International Arbitration”, 63 *Tulane Law Review*, 1989, 648 at 700.

mandatory obligations of municipal laws and statutes to be triable by public institutions established by the States. With humility and respect, one is in doubt whether in practical situation, we can still state that any issue is not arbitrable in Nigeria. This is because even the States in Nigeria refer revenue matters and taxes issues to private arbitral bodies to determine or resort to negotiation which is a form of ADR. Even in some of the sections of Administration of Criminal Justice laws in Nigeria, provisions are made where the courts are enjoined to advert the minds of the parties to ADR. In this age and era in Nigeria, plea bargain forms a necessary part of our criminal justice proceedings in Nigeria. Plea bargain starts with negotiation which is a form of ADR. In the Matrimonial Causes Act, the petitioner is required to attach a certificate showing that attempts were made at conciliation of the matter but it failed. Conciliation is also a form of ADR.

An award which violates the provisions of public policy laws of Nigeria will be subject to impeachment. We have both domestic and international public policy. Unfortunately, the Arbitration and Mediation Act did not define the meaning of public policy or its components. This is a very serious lapse because what is public policy varies from one State to another. However, public policy means “community common conscience, extended and applied throughout the State to matters of public morals, health, safety, welfare and the like, it is that general and well settled public policy opinion relating to man’s plain palpable duty to his fellowmen, having due regard to all circumstances of each particular relation and situation.”²⁸It means the principled guide to action taken by governments to address societal issues, encompassing the laws, regulations, decisions, and actions or inaction-taken to serve the public interest. It also means that which has a tendency to be injurious to the public or against the public good.²⁹In arbitration practice, public policy is interpreted narrowly to save arbitral award which otherwise could ordinarily be enforced. However, where arbitral award obviously violates the public policy of a State, the award will be impeached so as to safe public interest and morality.

g. Error of Law: Section 55(2) expressly provided that “an application to set aside an arbitral award shall not be made on the ground of an error on the face of the award, or any other grounds except those expressly stated in subsection 3.” Error of law is not expressly provided for in section 55(3) of the Act as a ground for impeachment, which by implication may be interpreted to mean that it cannot constitute a ground for impeachment of arbitral award in Nigeria. It must be noted that error of law is a common law provision and has never been in any of the provision of our Arbitration law or Act. In the repealed Arbitration and Conciliation Act CAP A18 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004, it was not expressly provided for in the Act but the Courts including the Supreme Court impeached arbitral awards based on application made pursuant to error of law.³⁰ Secondly, the word used in section 55(2) of the Act referred above merely made mention of the word “error” and not error of law. The implication seems that where there is error on the face of the award, the court to which an application is made for impeachment has jurisdiction to refer or remit the award to the arbitral tribunal to correct the error pursuant to section 55(6) of the Act. The error could be typographic or arithmetical error whereas error of law means a totally different thing. It is for this reason and more that we believe that arbitral awards are impeachable for reasons of error of law on the face of the award pursuant to common law. The provisions of section 55(2)

²⁸ *Black’s Law Dictionary*, 6th Edition, Centennial Edition, 1891-1991. 1231.

²⁹ *Egerton v. Brownlow* (1853)4HCL. 1

³⁰ *Taylor Woodrow Nig. Ltd v. S.E.W. GmbH* (1993)4 NWLR 425.

of the Act cannot constitute a complete barrier to impeachment of award for reasons of error of law on the face of the award. This is because a party to arbitration agreement cannot suffer an injury to go without a remedy merely because section 55(3) failed to provide for error of law. The law will always provide remedy for the injured party and the courts will obviously invoke the common law provision to advance a remedy for the injured party particularly as there are many decisions of the courts particularly the Supreme Court where error of law was a ground for impeachment of arbitral awards especially on issues where the error as complained by the applicant occasioned miscarriage of justice.

Error of law refers to any ruling, decision, or process that conflicts with the principles of the law. It refers to failure to correctly apply the law, leading to a violation of the litigant's right or miscarriage of justice in a matter. There are two types of error of law on the face of the arbitral award. The first is where what was referred to the arbitral tribunal is interpretation of the law or issues of law. If parties referred issues of law to the arbitral tribunal and error occurs, the court will not interfere because the parties know as of fact that arbitrators whether constituted by lawyers or laymen is not taken as a court. However where what was referred was facts but the arbitrators in evaluating the facts pretended to be lawyers and formulated principles of law in its consideration of the facts and hence committed error of law, the court will set aside the arbitral award because the arbitrators will be judge on the basis of their pretence and actions particularly if the principles of laws were wrongly applied and they occasioned miscarriage of justice against the party complaining.³¹

Where the ground for the application for impeachment of an arbitral award is basically on error of law, the applicant is restricted in his address to the court on the issues of the error as manifest of the face of the arbitral award or documents incorporated therein. For the court to hold that error of law has occurred in a matter of arbitral award, it has to be manifest on the face of the arbitral award. The court in *Ipswich Borough Council v. Fisons Plc*³² captured the situation very well when it held that;

It is not sufficient that he (judge) should have been in real doubt whether the arbitrator was right, nor I would add, does it matter whether the arbitrator's reasons may have been faulty, unless, this cast doubt upon his conclusion, it is always possible to arrive at the right answer for the wrong reason and in such case... he had at least, to be satisfied that there was a more or less strong *prima facie* reason for thinking that the arbitrator had erred on a question of law.

Sequel to the facts setout above, it is obvious that the standard of test is that of being satisfied that a strong *prima facie* case of error of law has been made to the satisfaction of the court to warrant tampering with the arbitral award. It is not one of merely thinking that the arbitrator erred on a question of law.

h. Misconduct: Misconduct is a technical term. It does not only mean issues of moral turpitude but also include cases of wrong handling of the arbitral proceedings and irregularity in arbitration. In arbitration, misconduct refers to an arbitrator's failure to act fairly, neutrally, or within their authority scope, constituting a breach of duty that can invalidate an award. It involves procedural injustice, bias, or serious errors, rather than simple mistakes in judgment, such as conflicts of interest, bribery, or denying a party the right to be heard and heard fully before an award was made.

³¹ *ibid*

³² (1990)Ch 709. *Clark (James Brush Materials) Ltd. V. Carters Merchant Ltd.* (1944) KB 56.

Section 55 (3) of the Act failed to expressly provide for misconduct of arbitrators as constituting a ground for impeachment of an arbitral award in Nigeria. The implication of section 55(2) of the Act is that arbitral award cannot be impeached for reasons of misconduct because the section provides that only the grounds specifically set out in section 55(3) could constitute grounds for impeachment. Section 30 of the repealed Arbitration and Conciliation Act CAP A18, 2004 provided expressly for the impeachment of arbitral award for reasons of misconduct. It is for this reason that we proposed that in further amendment of the 2023 Arbitration and Mediation Act, effort should be made to provide expressly for the impeachment of arbitral award for reasons of misconduct. The meaning of misconduct which we stated earlier had the components of the following; taking instructions or evidence from one party in the absence of the other party³³, acting beyond ones jurisdiction,³⁴ failure to act fairly either by ignoring critical evidence or documents and not acting in good faith, departure from established rules of natural justice, lack of neutrality, etc. All these elements of misconduct are included in the Arbitration and Mediation Act particularly section 55(3) (a) (iii) (IV) (v) and section 30 which specifically provided for equal treatment of the parties by the arbitral tribunal. The only lacuna is that the word misconduct was not specifically used in the Act. The simple implication of these provisions is that the Act provided for misconduct by incorporating its elements. The courts in *Taylor Woodrow v. S. E. W. GmbH*³⁵ and *A Savoia v. A. O. Sanubi*³⁶ enumerated these elements which constituted the basic elements of misconduct. The Supreme Court in *A. Savoia v. A. O. Sanubi*³⁷ listed the elements of misconduct as follows:

- (a) Where the arbitrator fails to comply with the terms express or implied, in the arbitration agreement;
- (b) Where even if the arbitrator complies with the terms of the arbitration agreement, the arbitration makes an award which on grounds of public policy ought not to be enforced;
- (c) Where the arbitrator has been bribed or corrupted;
- (d) Technical misconduct, such as where the arbitrator makes a mistake as to the scope of the authority conferred by the agreement of reference. This, however, does not mean that every irregularity of procedure amounts to misconduct;
- (e) Where the arbitrator or umpire fails to decide all the matters which were referred to him;
- (f) Where the arbitrator or umpire has breached the rules of natural justice;
- (g) If the arbitrator or umpire has failed to act fairly towards both parties, as for example;
 - (a) By hearing one party but refusing to hear the other; or
 - (b) By deciding the case on a point not put by the parties.

From the above decision of the Supreme Court of Nigeria, misconduct means a wide range of irregularities including but not limited to cases of breach of natural rules of justice and mishandling of the proceedings by the arbitrator.³⁸

³³ Section 30 of the Act.

³⁴ Section 55(3) (a)(iv) of the Act.

³⁵ *ibid*

³⁶ (2000)12NWLR (Pt.682)539 at 547.

³⁷ *ibid*

³⁸ Greg C. Nwakoby, "Setting Aside of Arbitration Awards in Nigeria- A Critical Review of the Case of Alhaji Alibashir & Sons Ltd v. B.U.K." *UNIZIK Law Journal*, 1999, 1.

We therefore conclude that misconduct remains a ground for the impeachment of arbitral award in Nigeria as all the material principles and elements of misconduct are found in section 55 (3) of the Act notwithstanding the misleading implication of section 55(2) of the Act.

3. Award Review Tribunal: The term Award Review Tribunal is not defined in the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023. Its meaning is missing in section 91 of the Act which is the interpretation section of the Act. An Award Review Tribunal (ART) is an optional, contractual, and appellate –level panel, introduced in the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023. It is designed to review an arbitral award for potential errors before the court intervention. Its review is usually based on the grounds set out in section 55(3) of the Act. Award Review Tribunal is an optional internal appellate level panel agreed by the parties to review arbitral award for errors instead of applying to court for impeachment of the award or refusal of enforcement of an arbitral award. It is optional in the sense that unless and until the parties to the arbitration agreement voluntarily agree to its application in their arbitration agreement, it shall not apply. The parties must specifically and explicitly agree to include Award Review Tribunal (ART) in their arbitration agreement. Section 56(1) provides that, “notwithstanding section 55(1) of this Act, the parties may provide in their arbitration agreement that an application to review an arbitral award on any of the grounds set out in section 55(3) of this Act shall be made to an Award Review Tribunal.” The implication of this is, that where such an agreement is reached by the parties to the arbitration agreement that Review Arbitral Tribunal shall apply to them, on the making of an arbitral award, a party who is dissatisfied by the terms of the arbitral award or the procedure thereof shall not file an application to court but should revert to the Award Review Tribunal. It is an internal appellate tribunal though not in the constitutional sense as Award Review Tribunal is not a court. The sole essence of it is for Award Review Tribunal to have a second look at the arbitral award with intent to remove errors and irregularities just as is applicable in ICSID Convention provisions. The only difference between the ICSID provisions and Award Review Tribunal is that under ICSID Convention, an application for annulment or impeachment has to be made to the second tribunal for determination and any award rendered by the second tribunal cannot be made subject to any court in any of the member States of ICSID because ICSID award cannot be impeached in any court. The courts of the member States have only one duty to perform and which duty is to enforce ICSID award and no more. Conversely, an award or decision rendered by the Award Review Tribunal under the Act can be made subject of contention in the courts in Nigeria. Section 56(2) provides that:-

Where the parties have agreed that an award shall be reviewed by an Award Review Tribunal, a party who is aggrieved by an arbitral award and who seeks to challenge the award on any of the grounds set out in section 55(3) of this Act shall, within the same time frame specified in section 55(4) of this Act, send the other party a written communication which indicates its intent to challenge the award (in this Act referred to as “**the Notice of Challenge**”).

From section 56(2) it is obvious that it is the agreement of the parties that drives the Award Review Tribunal. The grounds for the review are the same grounds for impeachment of arbitral award by the court. It is the same grounds for application to court for impeachment that constitute the grounds for review. The applicant for review is required to serve notice on the other party. The notice shall be accompanied by the original award or certified copy of it, the original arbitration agreement or the certified copy of it and where

the award or arbitration agreement is not made in the English language, a certified translation of it into the English Language.³⁹

The parties have right to agree as to the number of the arbitrators who shall constitute members of the Award Review Tribunal (ART). Where the parties failed to agree otherwise the number of arbitrators in the Award Review Tribunal shall consist of the same number of arbitrators in the arbitral tribunal that first determined the dispute which in the Arbitration and Mediation Act is referred to as “the First Instance Tribunal”.⁴⁰ When the tribunal is constituted, all the members are expected by the Act to accept their appointment individually. The Act did not state the manner and method of acceptance in this regard but it is expected that the arbitrator where he is a sole arbitrator or where they are more than one, shall accept their respective appointments in writing just as in ICSID Convention.⁴¹ The provisions of Arbitration and Mediation Act shall apply particularly as it relates to sections 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 30, 41, 44, 47, 50, 53, and 54.⁴²

The parties have right to agree on the applicable procedure to be followed by the Award Review Tribunal provided always that where the parties failed to specify the procedure, the Tribunal shall conduct the proceedings in a manner as it considers appropriate and shall endeavor to render its decision in the form of an award within 60 days from the date on which it is constituted.⁴³ Whichever procedure that is chosen must ensure fairness and equal treatment of the parties as provided in section 30 of the Act. The parties must be heard fully before decision is taken in their matter. The procedure may require invitation of witnesses for hearing and in which case matters may be reopened. Section 56(7) gives the impression that notwithstanding the application and notice for review, application could be made to the court for the enforcement of the award as made by the first instance tribunal.⁴⁴ The application or Notice of Challenge given to the other party ought to serve as a stay of proceedings on the matter until the Award Review Tribunal has finally disposed of the matter. Section 56(7)(a) gives the impression that stay could be granted during the pendency of the review but it did not state how such a stay could be applied for or granted. It would have been enough if the Act provided in section 56 that application or issuance of notice of challenge shall constitute a stay of proceedings in any court on issue of enforcement and impeachment in the matter.

The Award Review Tribunal has the right in its proceedings to set aside in whole or in part the award as made by the First Instance Tribunal. Where a party is dissatisfied with the setting aside in part or whole of the arbitral award as made by the First Instance Tribunal, the party may apply to the court to review the award as made by the Award Review Tribunal. Where the Court is satisfied that the decision of the Award Review Tribunal is unsupported having regard to the ground on which the Award Review Tribunal set aside the award, the Court shall reinstate the award or part of it that was set aside by the Award Review Tribunal.⁴⁵ In this section, the Act did not provide that the ground on which the Court may act may not be

³⁹ Section 56(2) of the Act.

⁴⁰ Section 56(4) (a) of the Act.

⁴¹ Section 56(4) (b) of the Act.

⁴² Section 56(5) of the Act.

⁴³ Section 56(6) of the Act

⁴⁴ Section 56(7) of the Act.

⁴⁵ Section 56(8) of the Act.

the whole grounds as set out in section 56(3) of the Act. Where the Award Review Tribunal has affirmed the award in whole or in part, an application to the Court to set aside the award of the First Instance Tribunal or that of the Award Review Tribunal may only be made pursuant to the provisions of section 56(3)(b)(i) or section 56(3)(b)(ii) of the Act.⁴⁶The challenge in this instance shall be for reasons of arbitrability or public policy or both.

Some have misconstrued the provisions of section 56(8) and 56(9) to mean that the challenge in court for the setting aside of the award as made by the Award Review Tribunal shall be for reasons that the subject matter of the award is otherwise not capable of settlement by arbitration under the laws of Nigeria, that is for reasons of arbitrability or that the award is against the public policy of Nigeria. This assumption is rather very wrong. Where the Award Review Tribunal set aside the arbitral award as made by the First Instance Tribunal, the applicant for impeachment is not restricted as to the grounds for impeachment. In this situation, he is at liberty to apply for the impeachment on any of the grounds in section 56(3) of the Act. The limitation as to grounds for challenge is only limited in situations where the Award Review Tribunal affirmed the award in part or whole. In this situation, the applicant may be limited to challenge on issues of arbitrability or public policy. It is important to note that the very word used in section 56(9) is that “the application **may** only be made on the grounds set out in section 55(3) (b) (i) or section 55(3) (b) (ii).” The word used in the Act is “May” which is not mandatory as it can be waived in deserving situations by the Court before which the application is made. According to some scholars there is high finality attained in the Award Review Tribunal exercise because of the provisions of section 56(8) (9). However such finality does not exist at all since there is provision for reverting to court at the end of the review. The finality in this instance could probably be attained if the application to a High Court is made the final court of trial on the issue of impeachment after the Award Review Tribunal decision. There is no finality in the legal sense since the application for impeachment of the Award Review Tribunal decision could go to High Court, Court of Appeal, and Supreme Court.

It must be stated herein that it is wrong for anybody to ever think that Award Review Tribunal provides a faster, cost –effective way to correct errors in award compared to the traditional court litigation, or that it enhances the efficiency of dispute resolution method. The procedure is never faster when we consider this against the attitude of an average litigant Nigerian or the Nigerian lawyer. This is because in most cases, the parties will still revert to court for impeachment of the arbitral award as made by either the Tribunal of First Instance or the Award Review Tribunal. Where parties agree as to Award Review Tribunal, parties often see it as a stepping stone to application for impeachment by the court. It is for this reason that the expected benefit of this provision may not be realized. In fact Award Review Tribunal has added an additional layer of complexity and potential delay in arbitration practice in Nigeria by creating an appellate process by laymen that narrows litigation and delays access to court for direct impeachment of arbitral award. It increases cost of arbitration and delays finality of arbitral award

To say that it is faster than application to court for impeachment because the time limitation for the review is 60 days as fixed in the Act is somewhat ludicrous. It is important to state that the 60 days can always be extended by the tribunal relying on section 66 of the Act. There is however, no guarantee that the review

⁴⁶ Section 56(9) of the Act.

must end within 60 days or that a court cannot entertain the impeachment within 60 days. There are still some effective and efficient courts in Nigeria which can insist on parties or litigants concluding their argument on impeachment of arbitral award within 60days.

On the issue of cost – effectiveness, it is very expensive to pay two sets of arbitrators on a single arbitration matter. Where the first arbitral tribunal has concluded its proceedings and handed down arbitral award, it seems better to refer the issue of impeachment to the court rather than to another arbitral tribunal. Can an arbitral tribunal by what name called, be an appellate tribunal to the arbitral award rendered by the First Instance Arbitral Tribunal? We do not think that this is neat and necessary. It is a new provision in our Arbitration Laws which some believed to be useful but we seemly believe that it is an unnecessary duality that will delay arbitration practice in Nigeria. Its functionality is in doubt. It will rather introduce delay than save time. It will introduce hardship to parties in arbitration because a recalcitrant party will still insist on filing application to court after the Award Review Tribunal must have made its award in the matter. In this situation, time and wealth will be wasted.

In the Arbitration and Mediation Act which introduced this new system of Award Review Tribunal, there is no provision that the award of the Review Tribunal can only be challenged in a High Court as a final court in the matter, that is, that the High Court shall be the final court for all challenges on the arbitral award on matters handled by the Award Review Tribunal. It would have been better if the High Court is made the final court of determination of arbitral award challenge in all cases where there is provision for Award Review Tribunal. This could have saved the day but as this is not a necessary part of the Act, the implication is that arbitral challenge after the Arbitral Review Tribunal must have made its award can still go on to the Court of Appeal, and Supreme Court respectively. This is unnecessary delay contrary to the basic philosophy of arbitration which is to promote efficiency and reduce delay in justice administration.

In most countries of the world review is often undertaking by the court. The essence of this is that once the court renders its decision, an aggrieved party can only go on appeal to a higher court. To introduce this second layer or level of arbitral tribunal at this stage will work hardship on the parties as it will certainly occasion delay in arbitration practice in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Impeachment is a necessary part of arbitration practice which boasts the moral of the parties in arbitration. It gives the assurance that where the expectations of the parties to an arbitration agreement are not met, there will be a second venue where the parties can ventilate their anger. The grounds for impeachment were presumably narrowed in the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 by implication of sections 55(2(3) of the Act. However, it is unacceptable that error of law and misconduct should be excluded as grounds for impeachment of arbitral award in Nigeria. Application for impeachment by an aggrieved party may be made to the court. However, we have seen that the Arbitration and Mediation Act 2023 has introduced a provision for Award Review Tribunal (ART).

Award Review Tribunal as defined above is an internal optional appellate tribunal agreed upon by the parties to the arbitration agreement. The essence of the Award Review Tribunal is to reduce or cut down on judicial interference and promote efficiency in arbitration practice in Nigeria particularly with respect to enforcement of arbitral awards. The duty of the Award Review Tribunal is to review the award on the

very grounds stipulated for setting aside an award in court. The Award Review Tribunal has jurisdiction either to set aside the arbitral award in part or whole or to affirm same in part or whole. In general, we hold the view that Award Review Tribunal is not cost efficient and is most likely to introduce unnecessary delay and hardship in the arbitration practice in Nigeria. Some of the basic advantages of arbitration are efficiency and speed, less expensive, confidentiality, handling of matter by experts, and eradication of undue delay. It is most likely that these advantages may be endangered in Award Review Tribunal system.